

DENOTATIVE AND CONNOTATIVE FEATURES IN THE TRANSLATION OF ARCHITECTURAL AND CONSTRUCTION TERMS

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Abstract In this article was analyzed cultural aspects of translation practice, cultural aspects of different languages require the translator to present cultural translation models, cultural districts based on the specific characteristics of that language. Adequate translation of construction and architectural terms does not depend only on their semantics or structure. The transfer of terms from the original language to the translation language also depends on their organic and logical, meaningful harmony with the context.

Key words: terms, translation, denotative component, terminological systems, dominant synonym, architecture and construction terms, specific signs, methods

Introduction

Every nation's culture has its own different forms, its customs in building constructions, production of raw materials and its preparation, distribution to the public also developed their own characteristics. There are certain reasons why this uniqueness of national mastery and craftsmanship creates wonderful architectural structures and enriches the lexicon of architecture and construction. Therefore, the national culture of that nation is directly reflected in the names of national buildings of each nation, in the construction of buildings and in the use of specific national terms in the construction process.

Materials and methods

There are several methods in the process of translating terms. However, some of them are active and some are inactive. Nevertheless, all of them have a

common character due to the novelty of the terms that appeared and the factors affecting their translation. Therefore, in the process of correct translation of terms, translators are assigned serious tasks, such as paying special attention to the requirements for the term and the factors influencing the choice of a certain translation method. Accordingly, the translator, having studied in detail some specific features of the language and traditions, can put forward an assumption or a hypothesis about which version of the translation will be the most successful and which will not work at all.

In the course of modern globalization, any person who has mastered any foreign language: a student, a journalist or a foreign language teacher tries himself at least once in the field of translation. However, their success in translation practice often ends in failure. The most correct conclusion is to explain the main reasons for this with the fact that the scientific and theoretical aspects of translation have not been thoroughly mastered. One such inconvenience is the process of denotation.

The root form of the denotation lexeme is denotate, which means the Latin denotare - to mark. An object is a known (named) reality or thing using a linguistic unit (for example, a word). The denotative meaning (or denotative component) is directly related to the perceived concept and serves to convey directly logically.

In architecture and construction, this process is inextricably linked with antonymy and synonymy. Therefore, the issue of antonymy and synonymy of terms is considered one of the most urgent and complex problems in linguistics today. In particular, the issues of the difference between synonymous terms and the concepts of synonymy in the general literary language have not yet been fully researched.

Synonyms (Greek synonymos - one-named) are lexical units that have the same denotative meaning, and the simpler explanation has the same general meaning.

The mutual meaning of language units is synonyms, which serve to express the thought in a clear and clear way, to be free of repetitions.

L. Kutina, who was specially engaged in the history of terminology, noted: "The widespread phenomenon of synonymy in the field of terminology is characteristic for the formation of terminological systems."¹.

In English, the terms architecture and construction are stable synonyms and are semantically related to each other by their denotative nature, and one serves to complement the other. One lexical unit in the line of synonyms is the main unit (main unit) and the rest of the synonyms are gathered around this unit. The main lexical unit is called a dominant synonym in the field of linguistics. The dominant synonym is the denotation of synonyms. Denotation refers to the central and primary meaning of a term. This situation is also observed in the terminology of architecture and construction industry. For example:

synonyms	denotate
<i>erector; constructor; designer; bricklayer, builder; stonemason; joiner; master</i>	
<i>edifice; building; construction; structure</i>	<i>builder</i>
<i>woodworker; carpenter; carver; cutter</i>	<i>building</i>
<i>roof ; house top; ceiling</i>	<i>carpenter</i>
<i>design; cadre; delineation; draft; layout; project; blueprint; scheme; device; plan</i>	<i>roof</i>
<i>tool; instrument; apparatus; gear; weapon</i>	<i>project</i>
	<i>instrument</i>

An important point in the practice of translation of architecture and construction terms in foreign languages is that the translation of each of the

¹L.Kutina Кутина Formation of Russian language theory. – М., 1974. – 278 p.

synonyms, taking into account their specific signs and characteristics, reflects the full meaning of the general context of the field. Another aspect observed in field practice is semantically equivalent terms. For example *wire - cable (sim); engineer - mechanic (muhandis); ruin - wreckage (xaroba va vayrona); ruins - remains (xarobalar va qoldiqlar); putridity - blight (chiriganlik); fragments - remnants (parchalar va qoldiqlar)* .

As in English, the process of synonymy related to architecture and construction terms is found in Uzbek and has its own place in translation. In this language, synonyms are formed around a concept according to their denotative nature, and it is more effective to present them according to their nature in the field of translation. For example, *quruvchi - usta, ip - arqon - kanat, chelak - paqir, qurol - asbob - dastgoh - anjom - uskuna*.

Based on our analysis, we found out that the terms representing personal names, i.e. anthroponyms, are given together with the denotation of a master, depending on their function in the field of architecture and construction. In the process of translation, translating based on their exact function will not be without benefit, of course. Including:

synonym	denotate
<i>gisht teruvchi</i>	
<i>tom (yopuvchi)</i>	
<i>suvoq</i>	<i>usta (si)</i>
<i>paxsakash</i>	
<i>loykash</i>	
<i>beton (quyuvchi)</i>	
<i>yog'och ustasi.</i>	

It should be noted that the composition of synonyms of the term in the languages in question may consist of one or more constituent parts (components). However, in the process of translation, this situation slightly distracts the form of the term from its denotative nature. Accordingly, first of all, it is a priority to determine the essence of their semantic features. For example, English: *fireplace*

ash pit cleanout door – trans.: kamin pech kuldoni tozalash eshigi; ash door – kuldon eshigi.

The peculiarity of English phraseological units in the process of translation is that they are connotatively diverse and quantitatively abundant. Until now, all the events that happened in Great Britain were reflected in the field of phraseology: political life, sports, cultural events, everyday life - this is not a complete list of topics reflected in English phraseological units, but only popular ones.

Conclusion

Most of the works on linguistics become obsolete, but they are constantly replaced by new, lively, bright and relevant ones that are subject to research analysis.

This kind of their polishing is a process inextricably linked with connotation. Thus, we can confidently say that among the new lexical units that will appear in the phraseological system of the English and Uzbek languages, language units related to the field of architecture and construction will develop day by day and will serve the formation of new phraseological units.

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